

Developing an *Ostreopsis* Early Warning System: the joint engagement of scientists, environmental agencies, and community science

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Abstract

In the last twenty years blooms of the harmful benthic dinoflagellate *Ostreopsis*, affecting human and environmental health, have become a common seasonal phenomenon in many temperate areas. Therefore, implementing an Early Warning System (EWS) of benthic harmful algal blooms (BHABs) is needed. While most routine monitoring programs are focused on plankton, collecting benthic samples is important in order to evaluate the stock of toxic microalgae. In the Mediterranean, several administrations have been conducting BHABs monitoring using scientific approaches in coordination with research centres. For an EWS to be effective, samples should be collected and processed soon and the results quickly communicated to the users. In the frame of the CoCliME project, an easy and reliable BHAB-sampling protocol was co-designed and implemented by scientists and stakeholders. Scientists produced and provided sampling kits and training sessions. Results (*Ostreopsis* abundance and risk level) were shared on coordinated online platforms between scientists and public agencies. This protocol has been successfully tested in Catalonia and France during the summers 2020 and 2021. It was proven to be an effective EWS for authorities to quickly raise recommendations on the health risks associated with *Ostreopsis* blooms in Mediterranean beaches. The protocol also contributes to build time series for elucidating climate change effects on *Ostreopsis* blooms.

Keywords: Early Warning System (EWS), Benthic Harmful Algal Blooms (BHABs), benthic microalgae, *Ostreopsis* blooms, community science, Mediterranean

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Introduction

The genus *Ostreopsis* was first described in tropical waters but in the last 25 years its biogeographic distribution has increased towards temperate latitudes where recurrent blooms are documented, in particular in the Mediterranean Sea (Vila *et al.*, 2001; Mangialajo *et al.*, 2011; Tester *et al.*, 2020).

Ostreopsis life history includes a plankton phase but it preferentially attaches to benthic substrates, such as macroalgae, other organisms, rocks, pebbles or sand, forming a mucilaginous matrix that covers the bottom. This benthic phase constitutes the reservoir of the *Ostreopsis* population which, in some circumstances can attain high cell numbers. Due to a combination of physical (wind, currents) and biological factors (migration), cells are released from the benthos to the plankton and also accumulates at surface. During huge blooms, the water colour turns brownish and floating foaming aggregates become visible at naked eye (known as “water flowers”).

Ostreopsis blooms have been linked to mortality of benthic fauna of scarce mobility (sea urchins, sea stars, crabs, etc.) (Shears and Ross, 2009; Illoul *et al.*, 2012) and it was linked (but not proven yet) to rare seafood poisonings fatalities in tropical areas (Randall, 2005). Luckily, such foodborne poisonings have never been reported in the Mediterranean (Kermarec *et al.*, 2008) where *Ostreopsis* blooms have been related with mild respiratory problems in people that stay near the seashore and inhale marine aerosol for several hours (Gallitelli *et al.*, 2005), experiencing symptoms such as rhinorrhea, pharyngeal pain, cough, general

malaise, headache, eye irritation and, and in occasions, fever ($\geq 38^{\circ}\text{C}$) (Vila *et al.*, 2016, and references there in). The concern of these blooms is reflected in the increased number of papers dealing about these BHAB species.

Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs) are a recurrent problem. In particular, *Ostreopsis* blooms have received special attention because, in addition to the just mentioned environmental and human health risks, they decrease the water quality of the Mediterranean beaches and can have an economic impact (Lemée *et al.*, 2012). However, the control of benthic harmful microalgae, such as the genus *Ostreopsis*, is not included in most routine monitoring programs in the world. The aim of this work is to present the Early Warning System (EWS) of benthic harmful algal blooms (BHABs) developed and tested in some beaches of Catalonia and France during the 2020 and 2021 summers to manage the risk posed by *Ostreopsis* blooms.

Material and Methods

For the EWS to be effective in providing information related to the bloom, three main aspects were considered: 1) reducing the time between sampling and results delivery, 2) training people to conduct the sampling (e.g., environmental agencies in Catalonia, Surfrider Foundation NGO in France) and 3) establishing a network of citizen/community contributors at stations where blooms are known to be recurrent.

A simplified protocol, adapted from the one used by scientists (e.g. as described in Moreira and Tester, 2016), was designed to

be applied by non-scientific people with the aim to quantify *Ostreopsis* abundance and to determine the associated health risks for humans exposed to aerosols and/or in direct contact with the seawater. Thus, previous knowledge on the *Ostreopsis* dynamics in the two study areas was used to define the period of study (from mid-June to the end of August or september) and to choose the number, location and frequency of sampling stations. The stations, selected based on previous information of *Ostreopsis* blooms occurrence plus people attendance to the beach, were monitored in the summers 2020 and 2021 with a variable frequency, every one or two weeks in Catalonia and from once a week (twice a week during blooms) to twice a month in France.

Sampling protocol

Macroalgae were collected by carefully picking them up by their base, placed in a flask with *in situ* seawater, shaken for a minute to detach their epiphytic cells and sieved through 200 microns mesh net. A picture of the seawater containing the released cells were taken at that time: it constituted a first indication of the presence and abundance of *Ostreopsis* in the sample. Immediately, microalgal cell samples were fixed with lugol. Macroalgae were slightly dried, extended on a white tissue paper, photographed, and stored in a fridge. Lugol fixed seawater and macroalgae were sent to the research institute. There, cell counts were conducted, and macroalgae were weighted. Cell counts were referred to grams fresh weight macroalga (g FW).

Scientists, samplers, and public agencies shared on the cloud the sampling protocol, a macroalgae identification guide, data

of the sampling day (meteorology, water temperature, salinity, sampled macroalgae, water volume of resuspension, pictures, etc.) and the results of *Ostreopsis* monitoring.

Cell counts were conducted at the research centres, but can also be done by trained personnel e.g. Surfrider NGO. The cell abundances were classified with colors, with a “Fire Light Scale” indicative of the thresholds and range values potentially related to health risks (Table 1), based on the experience in the area and in the literature (e.g., Funari *et al.*, 2015; Giussani *et al.*, 2017; Mangialajo *et al.*, 2017).

Results and Discussion

Management of BHABs requires established reference warning and alarm values. Five categories were established (Table 1): 1) not detected (blue); 2) presence ($\leq 2 \cdot 10^4$ cells g^{-1} FW; green); 3) moderate abundances ($2 \cdot 10^4$ to $2 \cdot 10^5$ cells g^{-1} FW; yellow); 4) high abundances ($\geq 2 \cdot 10^5$ cells g^{-1} FW; light brown), well established bloom, alert threshold; 5) abundances above $5 \cdot 10^5$ cells g^{-1} FW (red), alarm threshold for human health risk of *Ostreopsis*-related symptomatology. These colors were also consistent with the pictures taken by the samplers *in situ*. Thus, the first inspection of the sample when collected contributes to have an initial idea of the *Ostreopsis* abundance.

In Catalonia, in 2020, 44% of the samples collected in 13 stations exceeded the alert threshold, and the risk threshold was reached at least once in the 38% of the sampled stations (not shown).

In 2021, the risk threshold was attained in the 60% of the 20 sampled stations, although, symptoms were reported only in one station (not shown). To compare the two years, the mean, maximum and minimum cells concentrations were calculated for the same 10 stations sampled in both summers (Table 1). The alert (brown) or risk (red) thresholds were surpassed in six stations in 2020 and seven stations in 2021. Based on this, the intensity of the blooms in 2020 and 2021 were similar.

Station	2020				2021			
	n	Mean	Max	Min	n	Mean	Max	Min
Canyelles Petites	3	329.326	716.664	28.698	4	1.076.824	3.055.970	250.608
Sa Tarnardia	3	91.904	180.449	5.806	4	1.264.531	3.398.738	78.629
Mar Menuda	3	864.571	733.747	558.099	3	655.985	1.318.240	205.212
Pins Mar	7	1.850.663	3.413.467	498.321	6	866.761	2.595.445	47.493
Ponent	2	4.336	8.010	662	5	249.411	538.539	570
Ocata	2	1.007.228	2.014.455	0	3	794	1.737	124
Sant Miquel	3	215.591	357.564	2.203	4	206.727	357.541	1.492
Mota Sant Pere	3	246.494	499.569	263	5	141.073	205.687	17.121
La Mora	3	34.651	98.302	17	3	53.336	132.948	664
Cavet	3	125.803	313.834	5.151	6	619.1791	1.258.936	212.688

Abundance
 Benthic *Ostreopsis* sp. (cells /g FW)
 ● > 500 000 Risk level: very high concentration. Symptoms possible to occur
 ● > 200 000 Alert level: high concentration
 ● 20 000 - 200 000
 ● < 20 000
 ● Not detected

Table 1. *Ostreopsis* abundances (mean, maximum and minimum) in the 10 stations along the Catalan coast sampled in the 2020 and 2021 summers. The colors in the table correspond to the criteria shown below combining cell abundance and risk of experiencing *Ostreopsis*-related symptoms.

In Villefranche (France), in summer 2020, the *Ostreopsis* abundances surpassed three times the alert threshold and once the risk threshold (Fig. 1). The risk level in France was reached mainly in July, whereas in Catalonia it was reached in July, August and September.

The results on the abundance of *Ostreopsis* and the potential risk were communicated to the respective environmental or health administrations within a few days after samples were collected. Data were transferred

to the regional administration, the Catalan Water Agency in Catalonia and the Health Regional Agency in France, and also via RAMOGE, see further. If necessary, rapid contact was established with environmental technicians in the municipalities and / or regional Health Agencies, and warnings were given on the information panels of the affected beaches (Catalonia). In some stations, where the bloom is recurrent, an incipient net of community science contributors (including beach users, workers, and front-line residents) provided information to scientists when they observed the bloom or detected symptoms that could be related with *Ostreopsis* blooms.

Fig 1. Time plot of *Ostreopsis* in Rochambeau (Villefranche Bay, France) in summer 2020.

This surveillance is also structured with some coordination meetings among the different entities (Fig. 2). On one hand, the Water Catalan Agency organizes three meetings during the summer with environmental technicians in coastal city halls and scientists involved in the environmental programs, to identify the environmental status of the beaches. Analogous coordination exists in France among the LOV, the Surfrider NGO,

the Centre Antipoison de Marseille and the Health Regional Agency (ARS). The overall results and strategies are shared during regular RAMOGE *Ostreopsis* Working group (<http://www.ramoge.org>) with the participation of Italy and Monaco entities that conduct intensive and consolidated monitoring and research on *Ostreopsis* blooms.

Fig. 2. Diagram showing the flux of information between the different members involved in the EWS of *Ostreopsis*. LOV: Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche; CapTv: Poison Control Center of Marseille, France; ARS: regional Health Agencies, France.

This EWS has been successfully tested in Catalonia and France during the summers 2020 and 2021. It was proven to be an effective EWS for authorities to quickly raise recommendations on the health risks associated to *Ostreopsis* blooms in Mediterranean beaches. It also contributes to elaborate time series for elucidation of climate change effects on *Ostreopsis* blooms. This initiative is an example of the implementation of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) where researchers play a relevant role in the relationship between science and society.

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